

Studies on characteristics of palm seed fibre : An agro-waste for application in textile and non textile sectors

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Abstract : The palmyra or toddy palm (*Borassus flabellifera* L.) grows extensively in the coastal areas of Indian peninsula. Various edible products such as Neera, Jaggery, Sugar, Candy Chocolate etc. are produced from the soft, sweet and gelatinous pulp of the ripened fruit. However, the seeds after the extraction of pulpy juice are thrown away as agro-waste that contains fibres attached to its surface. Palm seed fibre was extracted from the seeds and its characteristics were studied. The fibre is characterized by creamy white in colour with a slightly yellowish tinge. The mean fibre length was found to be 8.71 cm. The average fineness value was found to be 9.29 tex. The fibre shows high extension at break not generally found in other vegetable fibres. The strength characteristics of raw and wet fibre were determined at 1 cm test length using instron tester. The soil burial test was carried out to determine the percentage retention of strength at different incubation periods. Spinning trials in combination with jute fibre showed satisfactory performance of blend with jute in ratio 30 : 70 (640 tex) and 40 : 60 (508 tex) respectively. Some handicraft products like Ladie's bag, Knot bag, Table mat etc. were developed from the palm seed fibre and the jute blend.

Keywords : Fibre, palm seed, soil-burial, fineness, tenacity.

Introduction

The palmyra is a tropical palm tree that grows indigenously in India, Srilanka, Malaysia, The Philippines, Indonesia and many parts of East Africa. It is prominent in the south Indian state of Tamilnadu where it was proclaimed the state tree in 1978, but can also be found throughout India in Kerala, Andhra Pradesh, Orissa, Bengal, Bihar and along the entire west coast¹. This multipurpose tree of great utility, figuring in history, literature and folklore, is exploited for food from the fruit and tuberous seedlings, beverage and the sugar from the sap, fibre from leaf and leaf base for brushes, trunk wood for construction and fuel and numerous minor products.

Results and discussion

Measurement of length and fineness :

The extracted fibre was spread on the paper and samples were drawn from different places at random to obtain the representative samples. The length of each fibre was measured with a scale, discarding fibres less than 3 cm. Its difficult to spin the short fibres (less than 3 cm) in jute spinning systems even after blending with jute at differ-

ent proportions. The frequency distribution of the length of the fibre was studied with group interval of 1 cm. The number and weight of fibres in each group was estimated and is given in Table 1. The fineness value of the fibre was calculated groupwise by dividing the weight of the

Table 1. Variation in length and fineness of the fibre

Sl. no.	Group interval (cm)	Frequency no.	Weight of fibre Mg	Fineness tex
1.	<3	-	-	-
2.	3-4	4	1.11	7.928
3.	4-5	18	9.57	11.814
4.	5-6	28	16.25	10.551
5.	6-7	22	12.00	8.391
6.	7-8	41	27.10	8.813
7.	8-9	40	26.61	7.826
8.	9-10	22	12.20	5.837
9.	10-11	16	13.80	8.214
10.	11-12	16	15.33	8.331
11.	12-13	15	32.20	17.170
12.	13-14	11	13.03	8.774
13.	14-15	16	18.33	7.900
14.	>15	-	-	-

fibre in each group to that of the total length and was expressed in the unit tex.

Statistical analysis :

To explore the nature of distribution of fibre length, the observed data was fitted with several distributions such as Normal and Gamma distribution. The Chi-square test was applied to identify the correct distributional pattern of the fibre length. The results obtained are shown in Table 2 which shows that, both the Normal and Gamma distributions were significantly fitted to the observed data.

Table 2. Test of significance for fitted distribution of the fibre length

Assumed distribution	Chi-square statistic	df (adjusted)	p-Value
Normal	37.306	10	0.00005
Gamma	44.99	10	0.0000

Table 3. Tensile properties of palm seed fibre (raw and wet)

Tensile property	Raw fibre	Wet fibre		
		24 h	48 h	72 h
Breaking load (N)	0.83 (49.92)	0.77 (55.53)	0.74 (42.14)	0.92 (52.78)
Ext. at break (%)	52.0 (44.55)	36.6 (57.32)	38.3 (50.74)	33.9 (51.45)
Tenacity (gf/tex)	9.13 (49.92)	8.46 (55.53)	8.07 (42.14)	10.06 (52.78)

Figures in parentheses shows the C.V. values.

Strength characteristics :

The results obtained for strength parameter data (breaking load, extension at break and tenacity) are given in the Table 3. The fibre is characterized by high breaking extension (52%), which is much higher than other natural fibres. However, the value decreased to the extent of less than 40% with wetting condition.

Both breaking load (0.83 N) and tenacity (9.13 gf/tex) of raw fibre reduced in wetting condition upto 48 h and shows a reverse trend beyond that period.

Soil burial characteristics :

The observations for strength retention of palm seed fibre were made at an interval of 24 h for six days and the number of filaments tested was 100 per sample. It is seen that, with the increase in the time of incubation, the percentage retention of strength of the fibre deteriorates (Fig. 1). The retention percentage falls to 45.89% on the sixth day. The extension at break during this period decreases from 52 to 13.5%.

Fig. 1. Retention of strength of palm seed fibre in soil burial condition.

Spinning characteristics :

Two spinning trials were conducted employing the small scale spinning technique normally used in the case of jute. The fibre was first treated with 20% oil in water emulsion with 40% application on the basis of weight of

the fibre. It was then passed through 72 pairs of rollers of the softner machine and binned for 72 h. Yarn has been spun in blend with jute in the ratio 30 : 70 (640 tex) and 40 : 60 (508 tex) respectively.

With further increase in the proportion of palm seed fibre, the yarn tenacity deteriorates. Two handbags, a table mat have been prepared as handicraft products from this blended yarn.

Experimental

Material and methods :

Extraction and evaluation :

Ripened fruits were collected from the local area. After removal of the pulpy tissue from the ripe fruits, the seeds were washed clean in cold water and sun dried. Fibre was collected through shearing the surface of the dried seed by a sharp blade keeping the blade as close as possible to the surface of seeds, so that fibres of maximum length are obtained. The fibres with branches were separated and each part was treated as a separate fibre.

Note

Measurement of strength characteristics :

The fibre strength was determined at 1 cm test length using Instron tester with the cross head speed of 1 cm/min and full scale load 2.5 N^2 . Both dry and wet strength was measured. The wet strength was measured at 24 h, 48 h and 72 h of soaking of the raw fibre in distilled water.

Soil burial test :

Resistance of fibre to microbial damage was determined by soil burial test³. Compost was prepared by standard method with air dried garden soil, cow-dung and sand in 2 : 1 : 1 ratio and moistened at 27% moisture. Bundle of fibre was buried in the compost in a 250 ml stoppered conical flask plugged with non-absorbent cotton and incubated at $30 \pm 1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Single filaments from the fibre bundle were taken out, washed with rectified spirit, air dried and tested by INSTRON for the retention in strength.

Spinning of extracted fibre :

The spinning trials were conducted with jute mill

machinery in the pilot plant of the laboratory. It was not necessary to pass the fibre through the breaker card as required for jute and other long vegetable fibres. The fibre was directly fed into the finisher card to produce sliver, which was again fed into the finisher card in blend with jute slivers received from the breaker card. The composite sliver from the finisher card was successively passed through the first, second and third drawing frame and then spun into yarn.

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